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Contributors

Katherine Briant, *TEI Encoder & Technical Assistance*

Katherine Briant graduated with an MA in Medieval Studies at Fordham University. She has assisted with encoding charters and creating charter pages.

James Doherty, *Supervising Scholar*

Heather Hill, *Design Lead & Project Supervisor*

Heather Hill oversaw the development of the Independent Crusaders Project, organizing assignments for each contributor and facilitating conversation as the project progressed. She also constructed the project website and created the map of departures using geospatial data extracted from charters, letters, and other documents related to each crusader. Heather also assisted in encoding the charters using the TEI guidelines.

Heather is a recent graduate from the MA program in Medieval Studies at Fordham. Beginning in the fall of 2016, Heather will be attending Pratt Institute as a student in their MLIS program.

Laura Morreale, *Project Contributor*

Robert Nayden, *Data Collection*

Andrew O'Sullivan, *Data Collection*

Nicholas Paul, *Supervising Scholar*

Nicholas Paul is Associate Professor of History at Fordham University. His publications include *To Follow in Their Footsteps: the Crusades and Family Memory in the High Middle Ages* and *Remembering the Crusades: Myth, Image, and Identity* (co-edited with Suzanne Yeager). He is currently working to edit and translate a collection of texts related to the independent crusader Manasses of Hierges. He is also working on a book project devoted to the use of the crusading frontier by western visitors, such as

independent crusaders. With Laura Morreale he has also co-edited a collection of essays entitled *The French of Outremer* forthcoming from Fordham University Press.

Dr. Paul oversaw TEI encoding of the crusader charters and contributed translations and summaries of several charters, as well as writing profiles of Thierry of Flanders and Fulk V of Anjou.

Stephen Powell, TEI Encoder and Technical Assistance

Alexander Profaci, TEI Encoder

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